

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

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РАЗРАБОТКА СПОСОБА ПОЛУЧЕНИЯ ЖЕЛЕЗОРУДНОГО КОНЦЕНТРАТА ИЗ МАГНЕТИТОВЫХ РУД

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DEVELOPMENT OF OBTAINING IRON ORE CONCENTRATE FROM MAGNETITE ORES

Аннотация

В данной работе рассмотрены возможности получения железорудного концентрата из магнетитовой руды. Изучен химический состав руды, рентгенофазовым анализом определен основной минерал магнетит Fe_3O_4 , с целью визуального изучения проведен петрографический анализ, установлено, что образцы неоднородны как по текстуре, так и по минеральному составу. Зерна магнетита характеризуются ксеноморфной, неправильной, пластинчатой и корродированной формой с рваными краями. Из-за повышенной отражательной способности можно предположить наличие слабой мартитизации. Пирит (FeS_2) встречается в форме отдельных мелких зерен, расположенных в микротрещинах, заполненных кварцем, а также в новообразованных участках кальцита. Проведен гранулометрический анализ дробленной руды класса – 25,0 + 0,0 мм который показал, что компоненты руды по содержанию равномерно распределены по фракциям. Для выявления оптимальных параметров предварительной сухой магнитной сепарации при напряженностях поля 500, 1000 и 1500 Э, эксперименты проводились на магнитном сепараторе РС-В 12/10-12.018. Полученный промпродукт измельчали на стержневой мельнице до фракции – 5,0+0,0 мм для раскрытия сростков минералов, после измельченный материал направляли на магнитную сепарацию. Исследования на обогатимость методом сухой магнитной сепараций проведены при напряженностях магнитного поля 500, 1000 и 1500Э. Таким образом, согласно данным исследований, обогащение магнетитовой руды включает в себя дробление, предварительную сухую магнитную сепарацию при напряженности магнитного поля 1000 э, дробление до класса крупности -5,0+0,0 мм и последующую сухую магнитную сепарацию при напряженности магнитного поля 1000 э.

Результаты исследований показали возможность увеличения содержания железа в концентрате при сохранении низкого содержания примесей, что способствует повышению качества концентрата.

Abstract

This study examines the possibilities of obtaining iron ore concentrate from magnetite ore. The chemical composition of the ore was analyzed, and X-ray phase analysis determined the primary mineral to be magnetite (Fe_3O_4). For visual examination, a petrographic analysis was conducted, revealing that the samples are heterogeneous in both texture and mineral composition. Magnetite grains are characterized by a xenomorphic, irregular, plate-like, and corroded shape with jagged edges. Due to the increased reflectivity, the presence of slight martitization can be assumed. Pyrite (FeS_2) occurs as individual small grains located in microcracks filled with quartz, as well as in newly formed areas of calcite. A granulometric analysis of crushed ore in the $-25.0 + 0.0$ mm class showed that the ore components are evenly distributed across the fractions. To determine the optimal parameters for preliminary dry magnetic separation at field intensities of 500, 1000, and 1500 Oersted, experiments were conducted on a magnetic separator RS-V 12/10-12.018. The obtained product was further ground in a rod mill to a $-5.0 + 0.0$ mm fraction to reveal mineral associations, after which the ground material was directed to magnetic separation. Studies on beneficiation by dry magnetic separation were conducted at magnetic field intensities of 500, 1000, and 1500 Oersted. Thus, according to the research data, the beneficiation of magnetite ore includes crushing, preliminary dry magnetic separation at a magnetic field intensity of 1000 Oersted, grinding to the $-5.0 + 0.0$ mm class, and subsequent dry magnetic separation at a field intensity of 1000 Oersted. The results of the study demonstrated the possibility of increasing the iron content in the concentrate while maintaining low impurity content, which contributes to improving the quality of the concentrate.

Ключевые слова: магнетитовая руда, керны, технологическая проба, дробление, минералогический состав, магнитное поле, магнитная сепарация, схема обогащения

Keywords: magnetite ore, cores, process sample, crushing, mineralogical composition, magnetic field, magnetic separation, enrichment scheme

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE ORE Core samples of ore after crushing to class $-25.0+0$ mm, all samples were combined into one technological sample,

from which samples for chemical, X-ray phase and petrographic analysis were selected to study the material composition. The chemical composition of the original ore is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Chemical composition of ore

No	Product name	Content, %					
		Fe	SiO ₂	S	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO
1	Source ore	36.75	22.54	0.25	6.96	5.64	1.94

X-ray phase analysis showed that the samples were mainly represented by the main iron mineral - magnetite Fe_3O_4 and pyrite FeS_2 ; and non-ore components were present in large quantities in the form of quartz, calcite, feldspar and chlorite, mica was found in small quantities. Petrographic analysis was carried out on specially selected larger samples of crushed ore. Seven polished sections were prepared from the samples. The samples were examined visually and microscopically using a Neophot-21 microscope.

In general, the samples from this deposit are heterogeneous both in texture and in mineral composition. The deposit was apparently formed as a result of contact between sedimentary rocks and granites and syenites, so the deposit should be classified as a contact-metasomatic type [1, 2].

Mineralogical composition

Magnetite – Fe_3O_4 is unevenly distributed in the samples, often observed in banded and lenticular formations. Magnetite grains also fill nests, i.e. pores in areas composed of calcite and cataclastic quartz. The sizes of magnetite grains range from 0.01 to 0.09 mm.

In the presented small-piece material it is difficult to characterize the structural and textural features of both the ore material and the rocks hosting the ore. Magnetite grains have a xenomorphic, irregular, plate-like corroded shape, i.e. with torn edges, their sizes are 0.01 - 0.09 mm. Since the reflectivity is higher, it is possible to assume the phenomenon of weak martitization.

In addition, in some areas, oolite relics are observed at the contact with high-temperature quartz, replaced by cryptocrystalline magnetite collected in rosettes, the so-called magnetite nodules.

In the non-metallic part, magnetite occurs in the form of small individual grains up to 0.012 mm.

The nature and form of magnetite distribution are difficult to determine in small lump material (Figure 1).

Pyrite – FeS_2 is found in the form of single small grains in microcracks filled with quartz, as well as in new formations of calcite.

Figure 1 – Character and form of magnetite distribution in the ore mass

a – plate-shaped corroded magnetite grains (white – magnetite, grey – calcite mixed with orthoclase, dark grey – quartz);

b – magnetite nodules in the form of nodules at the contact with orthoclase (white – clusters of magnetite micrograins, grey – orthoclase with distinct cleavage, dark grey – quartz, grey – calcite between nodules);

c – contact of oolitic nodules with high-temperature vein quartz (light grey – magnetite nodules, dark grey – vein quartz, yellow – pyrite, black – pore), x100

In addition, crushed pyrite grains are observed in nests and pores, they are mainly confined to areas composed of quartz, less often calcite. The sizes of pyrite grains range from 0.01 to 2.0 mm (Figure 2).

The non-ore mass is represented by highly metamorphosed quartz from finely dispersed to cataclastic, calcite - CaCO_3 , orthoclase and chlorite [3].

Figure 2 – Pyrite grains in the ore mass

a – single pyrite grains in a quartz vein (yellow – pyrite, dark grey – quartz, raw with distinct cleavage – calcite);

b – single xenomorphic pyrite grain in a relic of non-ore mass in highly cataclased syenite (pinkish-grey – orthoclase, dark grey – fine-grained quartz);

c – crushed pyrite (light yellow – pyrite, dark grey – quartz, light grey – magnetite nodules), x100

2.1 Preparation of ore for enrichment

In order to establish the distribution of the main components by size classes, a granulometric analysis of the ore was carried out. The selected sample was placed in a vibrating screen. Sifting was carried out through

sieves with a mesh size of 25.0 mm, 12.0 mm, 10.0 mm, 5.0 mm, 3.0 mm, for 15 minutes. The distribution of the main components of iron, silicon oxide, aluminum oxide and sulfur by fractions is shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Granulometric analysis of ore

Fraction	Product yield, %	Fe		S		SiO ₂		Al ₂ O ₃	
		content	extract	content	extract	content	extract	content	extract
-25.0 +12.0	9.0	29.65	7.13	0.24	9.52	29.72	12.36	8.01	10.61
-12.0 + 10.0	22.7	39.53	23.97	0.15	14.29	20.71	21.68	6.00	20.61
-10.0 + 5.0	35.1	37.61	35.25	0.27	42.86	20.71	33.53	6.60	35.15
-5.0 + 3.0	11.3	38.76	11.70	0.25	9.52	21.22	11.07	6.23	10.60
-3.0 + 0	21.9	37.48	21.95	0.25	23.81	21.16	21.36	6.92	23.03
	100.0		100.0		100.0		100.0		100.0

It follows from the data in the table that the ore components are uniformly distributed among the fractions by content, while the dependences of the extraction of components on the ore size have a parabolic dependence with maximum values corresponding to the average class - 10.0 + 5.0. Since selective separation of the useful component, in this case iron, is not practically carried out by any of the size classes, therefore, for further research we have chosen a range covering all the studied size classes, i.e. -25.0 + 0 mm.

To determine the optimal parameters of preliminary dry magnetic separation at magnetic field strengths of 500, 1000 and 1500 Oe, studies were conducted on a roller separator of type 138-T [4-6]. The results of magnetic separation are presented in Table 3. Analyzing the data in the table, it is evident that the optimal magnetic field strength is 1000 Oe, a further increase in magnetic field strength reduces the iron content in the concentrate, while the silicon dioxide content increases slightly.

2.2 Preliminary dry magnetic separation

Table 3

Results of dry magnetic separation

Field strength, Oe	Product name.	Product yield, %	Fe, %		SiO ₂ , %		S, %		Al ₂ O ₃ , %	
			contents	extracted	contents	extracted	contents	extracted	contents	extracted
500	magnetic fraction	72.68	46.98	92.19	14.75	48.03	0.21	72.00	6.00	55.61
	non-magnetic fraction	27.32	10.80	7.81	42.48	51.97	0.23	28.00	12.72	44.39
1000	magnetic fraction	76.90	47.88	95.02	14.80	53.52	0.18	73.68	5.38	61.15
	non-magnetic fraction	23.1	8.37	4.98	42.94	46.48	0.23	26.31	11.43	38.86
1500	magnetic fraction	77.94	44.39	94.96	15.66	59.10	0.20	76.19	6.37	67.50
	non-magnetic fraction	22.06	8.37	4.23	46.06	40.90	0.24	23.81	13.0	32.50

As can be seen from Table 3, the maximum iron extraction of 95.02 % was obtained at a magnetic field strength of 1000 Oe, while the magnetic concentrate contains Fe - 47.88 %; SiO₂ - 14.80 %; S - 0.18 %; Al₂O₃ - 5.38 %. A further increase in the magnetic field

strength to 1500 Oe led to a noticeable decrease in the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of enrichment, i.e. a decrease in the content and extraction of iron into the concentrate. This is probably due to the

fact that in a stronger magnetic field, magnetite "captures" particles of non-metallic minerals.

2.3.1 Magnetic separation class -5.0+0.0 mm

The obtained middlings were subjected to grinding in a rod mill to a size class of - 5.0 + 0.0 mm for 13 minutes in order to reveal the intergrowths of minerals.

Then, the ground middlings were sent to magnetic separation. The magnetic field strength was 500, 1000 and 1500 Oe. All the obtained enrichment products were sent to the chemical laboratory to determine Fe, SiO₂, S, Al₂O₃. The qualitative and quantitative characteristics of magnetic separation are shown in Table 4.

Table 4

Results of dry magnetic separation of middlings (class -5.0+0.0 mm)

Field strength, Oe	Product name.	Product yield, %	Fe, %		SiO ₂ , %		S, %		Al ₂ O ₃ , %	
			contents	extracted	contents	extracted	contents	extracted	contents	extracted
500	magnetic fraction	63.70	64.19	87.76	4.83	20.63	0.05	15.79	2.28	24.33
	non-magnetic fraction	36.30	15.72	12.24	32.64	79.34	0.46	84.21	12.44	75.67
1000	magnetic fraction	65.88	64.51	91.18	5.00	21.40	0.04	10.53	2.08	23.95
	non-magnetic fraction	34.12	12.04	8.82	35.41	78.60	0.49	89.47	12.76	76.05
1500	magnetic fraction	66.16	63.73	91.20	4.94	24.64	0.04	15.78	2.09	23.19
	non-magnetic fraction	33.84	11.70	8.80	30.85	75.36	0.46	84.22	13.49	76.81

As can be seen from Table 4, for the middlings of size class - 5.0 + 0.0 mm at 1000 Oe and 1500 Oe, the extraction of iron into magnetic concentrate is 91.18 % and 91.20 %, respectively, while for SiO₂ and S, a further increase in the magnetic field strength leads to an increase in their extraction into concentrate, which is explained by the mechanical "capture" of non-magnetic particles by magnetite.

A further increase in the magnetic field to 1500 Oe leads to an insignificant loss of iron, accompanied by a

noticeable increase in the content of silicon dioxide, sulfur and alumina.

Thus, according to research data, the enrichment of magnetite ore includes crushing, preliminary dry magnetic separation at a magnetic field strength of 1000 Oe, crushing to a size class of - 5.0 + 0.0 mm and subsequent dry magnetic separation at a magnetic field strength of 1000 Oe. The beneficiation scheme of magnetite ore is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Flow chart of magnetite ore enrichment

Conclusions

1. The objects of technological research were core samples with the following content by weight: Fe - 36.75; SiO₂ - 22.54; S - 0.25; Al₂O₃ - 6.96; CaO-5.64; MgO - 1.94. Chemical, X-ray phase, petrographic and granulometric analyses of the original ore were performed.

2. According to the petrographic and mineralogical analyses, the main ore minerals are magnetite – Fe₃O₄ and pyrite – FeS₂. Magnetite grains have a xenomorphic, irregular, plate-like corroded shape, i.e. with jagged edges, their sizes are 0.01 – 0.09 mm. The non-ore mass is represented by highly metamorphosed quartz from finely dispersed to cataclastic, calcite – CaCO₃, orthoclase, quartz – SiO₂ and chlorite.

3. Preliminary dry magnetic separation of crushed ore to a size of - 25.0 + 0 mm at a field strength of 500 -1500 Oe allows obtaining an industrial product

with an iron content of 44.39 % - 47.88 % with an extraction of 94.96 % - 95.02 %, respectively.

4. At the stages of magnetic enrichment, due to the fact that the main sulfur-containing mineral - pyrite is associated with a non-metallic mineral, i.e. quartz, it was possible to extract sulfur in the enrichment tailings up to 88 %, the resulting magnetic concentrate contains 0.03 - 0.04 % sulfur, which meets the requirements for iron ore concentrates.

5. The enrichment scheme allowed to obtain concentrates with iron content of 64.51 % and 66.29 %; and through extraction of iron from ore into concentrate of 86.88 % and 87.40 %, respectively. At the same time, the sulfur content in the concentrate was 0.04 % and 0.03 %, respectively.

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